

The Effectiveness of Policies to Accelerate the Elimination of Extreme Poverty in Indonesia (A Case Study on the Implementation of Presidential Instruction Number 4 of 2022 in Kediri County)

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ABSTRACT

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The purpose of this study is to describe and analyze the effectiveness of policies to accelerate the elimination of extreme poverty in 2024, including in Kediri County. This research process uses a qualitative approach and the type of research is a case study, which was conducted in Kediri County, East Java Province, Indonesia. The research was conducted with in-depth interviews with 6 (six) key informants from 7 (seven) Regional Apparatus Work Units (SKPD) who are considered to represent SKPD. The focus of this research is the effectiveness of policies to accelerate the elimination of extreme poverty. Data collection techniques using interviews for primary data and documentation for secondary data. The analysis technique used content analysis. The conclusions of this study are: First, The Central Government has issued Presidential Instruction Number 4 of 2022 concerning the Acceleration of the Elimination of Extreme Poverty. Kedua, The implementation of Presidential Instruction Number 4 of 2022 requires integration, synergy and cooperation between ministries and local governments, so that Ketiga, the effectiveness of the implementation of policies to accelerate poverty eradication is less effective due to communication system constraints in cooperation between ministries and local governments, especially in human resource management and funding.

KEYWORDS:

effectiveness, policy, extreme poverty

INTRODUCTION

On June 8, 2022, the government (central) issued Presidential Instruction Number 4 of 2022 concerning the Acceleration of the Elimination of Extreme Poverty, hereinafter referred to as "INPRES." This Presidential Instruction aims to accelerate the eradication of extreme poverty in Indonesia and the target is achieved by 2024. The government has set and committed and strives hard to reduce extreme poverty to zero percent (0%) by 2030. Countries in the world, including Indonesia, which supports the Sustainable Development Goals or hereinafter referred to as the SDGs, understand that the first goal is End Poverty and unlike other countries, President Joko Widodo intends

to end extreme poverty by the end of 2024 or six years earlier than the SDGs target. The definition of extreme poverty is a condition of people's welfare at a position below the extreme poverty line or equivalent to 1.9 \$ US or Rp 30,400.00 (curs 1 \$ = Rp 16,000.00) Purchasing Power Parity (PPP) per day. Extreme poverty is measured using an "absolute poverty measure" that is consistent between countries and between times. Rahmatullah stated that related to extreme poverty, the choice of social welfare service and rehabilitation programs is the first or the government's main choice in the framework of poverty alleviation with the mainstreaming of the SDGs, especially in the first goal, namely End Poverty (Rahmatullah et al., 2021)

The need to create integration between ministerial agencies in this INPRES is because problems and challenges faced in the field can be effectively resolved. To be effective, the implementation of the program requires good teamwork and relations with the mass media as well as coordination between ministries and a good management information system. The Integration Model is designed both horizontally and vertically, in order to create a unity and unity of a whole and undivided relationship, so that it is more focused on

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solving the problem of reducing extreme poverty (Humaira et al., 2024) (Sumarnni & Yuningsih, 2020); (Tanjung, 2020); (Afuddin, 2022); (Li et al., 2022); (He & Tang, 2021)

In addition to integration in reducing extreme poverty rates, synergy is needed across all ministries by establishing communication, coordination and collaboration. Synergy can be realized if a memorandum of agreement is made, either in the form of a memorandum of understanding (MoU) or Cooperation of Agreement (CoA). Then, the Ministry ensures access to comprehensive information and formulates a risk management, so that the reduction of extreme poverty rates can be faster than December 2024 effectively and efficiently. Then, the Ministries agreed to create standard operating procedures regarding communication and coordination and participation, so as to create a harmony of all activities in the context of reducing extreme poverty rates. All activities of the Ministry must be based on a performance system in the sense that all activities can be measured by inputs, outputs and outcomes indicators (Anggalaksana, 2022); (Poespithadi et al., 2023); (Nurhayati et al., 2020); (Angga & Pradana, 2021); (Feizabadi & Alibakhshi, 2022); (Leibensperger et al., 2021); (Zhu et al., 2021); (Patil et al., 2021)

Cooperation between ministries to reduce extreme poverty is needed because the implementation of this governance collaboration requires effective and continuous communication and coordination is not limited by hierarchy and sectoral egos to facilitate between actors, so their role in developing relationships is important. The success of the extreme poverty reduction program requires budget policy instruments that favor the poor, so all ministries must cooperate closely in the implementation of program policies and performance-based budgets for effectiveness in handling extreme poverty (Putri et al., 2024); (Sulaiman, 2021); (Latifa, 2023); (Supriyanto & Jannah, 2022); (Taruno et al., 2022); (Septiana & Tohopi, 2024)

Therefore, a cooperation strategy was formulated to realize the strengthening of cross-sectoral regulations, risk reduction, realize the strengthening of an adaptive and responsive risk reduction management system, and realize the development of a cooperative system. Cooperation between ministries is needed to be effective, so innovation and institutional strengthening as well as sustainable development management are needed (As' et al., 2024); (Alaufa et al., 2022); (Yunita et al., 2024); (Kholis & Lubis, 2021); (Rumkel et al., 2020); (Oktawirani, 2023)

Cooperation between sectors or ministries must be based on the principle of openness to receive input from both fellow ministries and community groups. Cooperation is also required to have mutual trust and mutual understanding of the conditions of each Ministry. In addition, there needs to be a clear division of duties and responsibilities, so that it is carried out optimally. Cooperation between sectors or ministries must be based on the principle of openness to receive input from both fellow ministries and community

groups. Cooperation is also required to have mutual trust and mutual understanding of the conditions of each Ministry (Mashita et al., 2023); (Huwaida, 2021); (Ali et al., 2021); (Pearce et al., 2020)

Furthermore, the President of the Republic of Indonesia asked his aides to accelerate the process of alleviating extreme poverty in a targeted manner through policy strategies such as reducing the burden of state spending, increasing state revenue, and reducing the number of poor groups. The two directives were conveyed to several ministers and heads of institutions as well as all governors and regents/mayors and in their implementation, coordinated by the Vice President as the Chairman of the National Team for the Acceleration of Poverty Alleviation. President of the Republic of Indonesia Joko Widodo as head of state is determined to eliminate extreme poverty in all regions of the Republic of Indonesia until the end of 2024 or December 31, 2024, through the integration and synergy of programs, as well as cooperation between ministries, as well as institutions and local governments, as shown in table 1 below: Furthermore, the President of the Republic of Indonesia asked his aides to accelerate the process of alleviating extreme poverty in a targeted manner through policy strategies such as reducing the burden of state spending, increasing state revenue, and reducing the number of poor groups. The two directives were conveyed to several ministers and heads of institutions as well as all governors and regents/mayors and in their implementation, coordinated by the Vice President as the Chairman of the National Team for the Acceleration of Poverty Alleviation. President of the Republic of Indonesia Joko Widodo as head of state is determined to eliminate extreme poverty in all regions of the Republic of Indonesia until the end of 2024 or December 31, 2024, through the integration and synergy of programs, as well as cooperation between ministries, as well as institutions and local governments.

The problem raised in this study is whether the policy to accelerate the elimination of extreme poverty in 2024 is effective, including in Kediri Regency? Meanwhile, the purpose of this study is to describe and analyze the effectiveness of policies to accelerate the elimination of extreme poverty in 2024, including in Kediri Regency Literature Review. Strong collaboration between different parties can create integrations to successfully overcome challenges and provide protection. The implementation of a program requires maximum integration, so good teamwork is needed and the existence of an organization that helps in its realization is the mass media. In addition, in the implementation of the program, there is also a need for coordination between related agencies. Integrating all information systems in an organization can effectively add value to the organization (Humaira et al., 2024) (Sumarnni & Yuningsih, 2020); (Tanjung, 2020). For case, within the integration design related to integration, specifically the

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design of integration frameworks in SMP and Pesantren Bumi Cendekia is partitioned into three, specifically the concept of an coordinates vision and mission, organization integration; integration of educational modules and learning; and administration related to arranging, execution, and assessment of the integration of pesantren instruction with school instruction in SMP and Bumi Cendekia Islamic boarding schools in Yogyakarta (Afuddin, 2022)

This study's discoveries depict unused thoughts found by comparing urban agglomeration approaches, which is accommodating to get it the premise of defining urban agglomeration improvement arranging arrangements in China, and see forward to the long-term arranging for the advancement of territorial integration characteristics in China. Integration is illustrated not as it were on a level plane but moreover vertically, rising above public-private boundaries. The central part of essential care is exceedingly noticeable in nearly all the integration models. In any case, these models are related with a assortment of downsides in connection to capacity, recognition, and operation that require advance insightful and approach examination, demonstrating the strength and tirelessness of siloed healthcare hones (Li et al., 2022); (He & Tang, 2021)

Ideally, empirical institutional synergy must be supported to maintain the stability of communication, coordination, and cooperation. Efforts to increase synergy between organizations through strategies to strengthen memorandums of understanding between organizations and a guide for understanding and agreement in among pertinent partners and give budgetary bolster and include work force (Anggalaksana, 2022); (Poespithadi et al., 2023). The key to successful management learning lies in cross-organizational coordination to ensure a holistic approach and mature risk management, as well as operational integration across all lines, thereby increasing efficiency in terms of service time and profits (Nurhayati et al., 2020). Among educate had synergized well in terms of communication and coordination as prove by the conveyance of data, participatory and understanding between the teach, the interest and understanding were in agreement (Angga & Pradana, 2021)

Organization movement likes within the setting of mechanical markets, and particularly the car component industry, a complementary interaction impact is found between coordination and participation. Taking after that, a partner collaboration approach is connected to synthesizing ordinary reactions of partners. Based on the discoveries of insufficient partner synergy Our comes about refine the existing supply chain integration by highlighting the complementary impact of coordination and participation. Efficiency dominates the synergistic development of the system and a significant spatio-temporal difference is observed in the synergistic evolution of institutions resilience and efficiency (Feizabadi & Alibakhshi, 2022); (Leibensperger et al., 2021)

(Zhu et al., 2021). The subsidizing issues and mechanical complexities are interrelated and require synergetic participation between blockchain engineers, givers, helpful associations and other helpful supply chain partners. Encourage, "lack of mindfulness and understanding among stakeholders" and "interoperability, collaboration and cross-pollination among compassionate organizations" were recognized as slightest compelling boundaries to square chain innovation appropriation in helpful supply chain (Patil et al., 2021)

The implementation of governance collaboration requires effective communication to facilitate between actors, so their role in developing relationships is important The process of collaboration between institutions requires continuous communication, coordination without hierarchy boundaries and avoiding sectoral egos, to improve work programs. The process of collaboration between institutions requires continuous communication, coordination without hierarchy boundaries and avoiding sectoral egos, to improve work programs (Sulaiman, 2021); (Latifa, 2023) (Putri et al., 2024). The success of the program needs to be supported by a high level of integration and the strengthening of several policy instruments to realize this high level of policy integration. Understanding the dynamics of collaboration between institutions in handling problems is expected to be a reference to increase the effectiveness of handling other problems (Supriyanto & Jannah, 2022); (Taruno et al., 2022); (Septiana & Tohopi, 2024)

Therefore, the formulated strategy can realize the strengthening of cross-sectoral regulations, risk reduction, realize the strengthening of an adaptive and responsive risk reduction management system and realize the development of a cooperative system (As' et al., 2024)

This can be realized through the participation of high stakeholders, the commitment of local leaders, and the absence of local egos. Meanwhile, the obstacles are differences in regulations, lack of discipline, gaps in results (data), and incompetent human resources (Alaufa et al., 2022). Triple Helix competes simultaneously and the scope of the institutions that work together differs from situations with inter-agency coverage. It also differs from a separate institutional field, at least in theory following laissez-faire principles. From one of these starting points, there is a movement towards a new global model for dynamic innovation analysis. The role of individuals and cooperation across sectors and groups is expected to strengthen inclusive and harmonious institutions integration. Awareness and concern for diversity is an important foundation to be able to build a strong and inclusive institutions integration (Yunita et al., 2024); (Kholis & Lubis, 2021)

This shows the partnership relationship between institutions, shows effectiveness in communication the types of innovations, the role of the parties, especially the management of sustainable development. Some

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strengthening institutions, among others: 1) the inventory of types of innovation; 2) The role of stakeholders; 3) strengthening policies; 4) Facilitating the strengthening of quality services; 5) co-creation between the community and personal (Rumkel et al., 2020); (Oktawirani, 2023). The conclusion is, open discussion forums, develop closer interpersonal relationships, hold meetings for all stakeholders, conduct comprehensive and routine education for society, increase promotion, seek funding assistance, and provide opportunities for society according to their respective roles (Mashita et al., 2023)

The process of health development is inseparable from cooperation between various sectors. Good coordination is needed to support optimal development results. Clarity is needed in the strict division of roles and responsibilities between the sectors involved so that development can be carried out optimally (Huwaida, 2021). The categories were weaved together to generate a core category that indicates that development agencies specialising in different areas need to work with indigenous communities in interdependent and complementary partnerships for sustainable development in Pakistan. We offer our recommendations to accomplish genuine interdependent and complementary partnerships (Ali et al., 2021)

We suggest the five key benefits to collaboration and show that with trust, understanding, and mutual respect, powerful and sustainable partnerships develop. Such trust and respect are hard won, but once established, sustain a high level of commitment, enable development of shared long-term visions of success, and attract diverse funding streams (Pearce et al., 2020). The high and low Gross Regional Domestic Product (GDP), Human Development Index (HDI), and per capita expenditure have a significant effect on the percentage of poverty (Aprilianti et al., 2022) On the contrary, the condition of sanitation, electricity and road infrastructure has a significant negative effect on the poverty rate, in the sense that the improvement in each infrastructure has an impact on decreasing the percentage of poor people in Indonesia. Thus, it is proven that the increase in each element of sanitation, electricity and roads has a significant effect on reducing the percentage of the poor population in Indonesia (Andrianus & Alfatih, 2023)

In the event of a reduction in poverty, local governments should focus their policies on improving the quality of human resources in terms of improving health, education, skills and expertise. Thus, people have the competence to compete and get better jobs, which can ultimately increase income and life welfare so that they are not trapped in the cycle of poverty. The Physical Special Allocation Fund for education, health, poverty and economic growth has a significant effect on the value of the Human Development Index (HDI) in the region (Dewi, 2023);(Saiful & Jumading, 2023). The Social Welfare Service and Rehabilitation Program is the first or the government's main

choice in the framework of poverty alleviation with the mainstreaming of the SDGs the Social Welfare Services and Rehabilitation Program is first ranked or the first choice in the framework of poverty alleviation by SDGs mainstreaming (Rahmatullah et al., 2021) Reality conditions, the facts were obtained which could later be verified. become capital in handling out of School Children ("Anak Tidak Sekolah/ATS") to tackle Extreme Poverty and Stunting and this study describes qualitatively descriptive cultural barriers in poverty reduction in Indonesia (Kurniawan et al., 2022); (Arifin, 2020); (A. W. Pratama et al., 2022)

A results show that problems related to objective and targeted regional BANSOS interventions need data governance based on a management information system that can map and classify based on the types and attributes of BANSOS sourced from the APBD (Saputra et al., 2023). The results of the study are that the number of Indonesia's poor population from year to year has decreased by an average of around 946,330 from 2015 – 2018. The results of the study show that 1) HDI does not have a positive effect (opposite) which means that when HDI rises poverty will decrease, 2) the level of education does not have a positive effect (opposite) which means that when the level of education rises poverty will decrease, 3) the unemployment rate has a positive effect which means that when the unemployment rate decreases, the poverty rate also decreases 4) HDI, The level of education, the unemployment rate turns out to have a simultaneous effect on poverty in Indonesia. The conclusion in this study is that it turns out that HDI, education level, and unemployment rate are affected partially or simultaneously (Sopian, 2020); (Purwadinata, 2024)

Average length of schooling (RLS), life expectancy (AHH), per capita income and poverty rate. The method used is multiple linear regression. The results showed that RLS had a significant negative effect on the poverty rate while AHH and per capita income had a negative and significant effect on reducing the poverty rate (Salong et al., 2024). Researchers provide suggestions for expanding the stakeholder base by involving academics and the mass media, improving the quality of resources, encouraging inclusive and active participation from all stakeholders, increasing the role of the community in community empowerment, setting a regular meeting schedule to conduct face-to-face dialogue, forming a formal agreement in every collaboration that will be carried out, creating an organizational structure and division of roles for each stakeholder involved in collaboration, collaborating with parties from the corporate sector through CSR partnerships (Ramadhani et al., 2024)

The results of the estimation show that there is a short-term influence of economic growth, unemployment and inflation on poverty, while in the long term economic growth and unemployment rate have a significant effect, while inflation is not significant. Simultaneously, it is concluded that the independent variables overall affect the poverty level

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(Payapo et al., 2023); (Fajar & Nurfalalah, 2020). ICT utilization should develop various job training to improve their abilities by using digital tools to live more productively in all corners of Indonesia. The results show that theoretically MSMEs are very likely as an exit strategy for poverty in Indonesia. MSMEs have very strong probabilities as representative ways out for poverty alleviation in this country (Azzasyofia, 2022); (Rachmawati, 2020)

Policies can help smallholder farmers connect to this “hidden middle” in more gainful ways and help them climb out of poverty as well. I suggest that poverty-reduction strategies can represent sound and effective methods for reducing tropical deforestation. These findings will facilitate development of sustainable strategies that will both reduce deforestation over long term and reconcile forest conservation with social welfare (Rob & Cattaneo, 2021); (Miyamoto, 2020). Poverty alleviation initiatives have achieved significant successes, there are still several challenges that should be of concern in the coming years, such as the diminishing marginal effect of financial inputs on poverty alleviation, the resulting negative incentives for the poor to improve their internal motivations and the insufficient participation of markets and social forces in poverty alleviation. It is urgent to introduce successful experience and typical modes of global human-earth system coordination and sustainable development and contribute to building a community of human destiny (Liu et al., 2020); (Yang & Liu, 2021); (Diwakar & Shepherd, 2022)

RESEARCH METHODS

This research process uses a qualitative approach and the type of research is a case study, which was conducted in Kediri Regency, East Java Province, Indonesia. The research was conducted by in-depth interviews with 6 (six) key informants from 7 (seven) Regional Apparatus Work Units (SKPD) who are considered to represent SKPD, namely: Regional Development Planning Agency/Bappeda (DN, 40 years old), Social Service (HR, 56 years old); Manpower Office (AB, 51 years old); Cooperatives and Micro Enterprises Office (ST, 52 years old); Marine and Fisheries Service (YL, 50 years old); Trade Office (ID, 46 years old); Industry Service (HR, 45 years old). Meanwhile, secondary data sources from their respective offices. The focus of this

research is the effectiveness of policies to accelerate the elimination of extreme poverty. The data collection technique uses in-depth interviews for primary data and documentation for secondary data as an additional explanation of the data collected through in-depth interviews. The analysis technique is used content analysis from the collection of data from the above data sources and for data reliability triangulation is carried out, namely data sources by aligning the data obtained with data from key informants. Furthermore, transferability is determined so that it can be worn in other conditions. Therefore, theoretically the same results can be achieved in several other conditions. After that, dependability and reliability are determined with the intention that the results are fixed and consistent. The degree of dependence is an indicator to measure the quality of the research process. In the last process, confirmability is established as a criterion to assess the quality of research results with an emphasis on data tracking and interpretation supported by existing data with certainty check techniques.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The problem of poverty in Kediri County is exacerbated by several important factors. *First*, inaccurate poverty data causes discrepancies between the actual number of poor people and official figures, thus hindering the effectiveness of aid distribution. *Second*, the provision of assistance to the poor is still less than optimal and often fails to meet their basic needs. *Third*, the support provided is often not on target, and those who really need it often receive inadequate support. In addition, the lack of interest and awareness of the poor in the importance of education leads to low educational attainment, reduced job opportunities and improved quality of life. *Fourth*, many poor families live in inadequate housing, poor physical conditions, and lack of access to basic facilities such as clean water and sanitation. Integrated and sustained efforts are needed to address these problems, including validating poverty data, distributing targeted assistance, raising awareness of the importance of education, and improving living conditions. The obstacles that occur in the field are a reality that is "given," namely (DN and HR): (1) the head of the family of elementary school graduates; (2) female heads of families; (3) family members with disabilities; (4) inadequate sanitation facilities.

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Figure 2. Percentage of Extreme Poverty in Kediri District, 2021-2023

Source: Coordinating Ministry for PMK, Year 2024-RKPD Year 2025

As part of the implementation of Presidential Instruction Number 4 of 2022 concerning the Acceleration of Extreme Poverty Alleviation, the Deputy for Coordination for Social Welfare Improvement as the Chairman of the Task Force for Data Management for the Acceleration of Extreme Poverty Elimination (P2KE Data Management Task Force) appreciated and expressed his gratitude for the commitment, cooperation, and contribution of all local governments to date. Furthermore, to encourage efforts to overcome extreme poverty in Indonesia quickly and sustainably, the results of the calculation of the estimated extreme poverty rate at the district/city level in 2023 were submitted. This calculation was obtained through a comprehensive analysis carried out by the Task Force for Data Stewardship for the Acceleration of Extreme Poverty Alleviation (P3KE Data Stewardship Task Force), under the coordination of the Coordinating Ministry for Human Development and Culture.

Regarding the problems mentioned above, several important notes were conveyed as follows: The estimate of

the extreme poverty rate at the district/city level in 2023 is not an official poverty statistic. This figure is specifically taken into account as an internal reference for local governments, especially as a tool to find out and evaluate the results of efforts to accelerate the process of eliminating extreme poverty (PPKE) at the Regency/City level in 2023; The estimate of the extreme poverty rate at the district/city level in 2023 can be used as a basis for planning and allocating the PPKE budget according to the district/city area in 2024; The Governor as a representative of the Central Government in the regions, in carrying out the function of coaching and supervision based on Presidential Instruction Number 4 of 2022, can use the estimated number of extreme poverty rates in districts/cities in 2023 as a basis for coordination and ensure that the PPKE in each region reaches the 0% target by 2024.

The data on the estimate of the extreme poverty rate can be seen in table 3 below.

Table 3. Estimation of the Level and Number of Extreme Poor Population in East Java Province 2021-2023

No	Code	County/City Name	Estimated Number of Extreme Poverty (thousand people)			Estimated Extreme Poverty Rate (%)		
			2021*	2022*	2023**	2021*	2022*	2023**
1	35.00	East Java Province	895.71	724.33	333.76	2.23	1.80	0.82
2	3501	Pacitan	3.78	5.29	1.39	0.68	0.95	0.25
3	3502	Ponorogo	4.04	5.83	0.00	0.46	0.66	0.00
4	3503	Trenggalek	6.73	10.63	0.00	0.96	1.52	0.00
5	3504	Tulungagung	9.83	0.00	0.00	0.94	0.00	0.00
6	3505	Blitar	5.22	9.30	3.36	0.45	0.79	0.29
7	3506	Kediri	21.60	47.60	12.25	1.36	2.99	0.77
8	3507	Malang	37.87	24.07	8.08	1.44	0.91	0.30
9	3508	Lumajang	18.89	13.56	5.16	1.80	1.29	0.49
10	3509	Jember	41.09	26.79	7.58	1.66	1.08	0.30
11	3510	Banyuwangi	17.14	16.10	7.05	1.06	0.99	0.43
12	3511	Bondowoso	20.12	11.67	13.23	2.57	1.49	1.68

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13	3512	Situbondo	18.24	6.01	2.49	2.65	0.87	0.36
14	3513	Probolinggo	51.69	37.74	27.22	4.38	3.18	2.28
15	3514	Pasuruan	21.49	25.79	7.61	1.30	1.56	0.46
16	3515	Sidoarjo	36.66	31.03	11.13	1.58	1.32	0.47
17	3516	Mojokerto	15.74	17.73	15.05	1.39	1.55	1.31
18	3517	Jombang	29.51	11.88	6.39	2.32	0.93	0.50
19	3518	Nganjuk	11.81	14.40	5.69	1.11	1.36	0.53
20	3519	Madiun	13.52	13.06	4.12	1.97	1.90	0.60
21	3520	Magetan	12.26	9.34	0.00	1.93	1.47	0.00
22	3521	Ngawi	20.68	12.30	13.73	2.46	1.46	1.63
23	3522	Bojonegoro	36.14	22.43	22.01	2.88	1.78	1.75
24	3523	Tuban	62.05	61.18	12.58	5.25	5.16	1.06
25	3524	Lamongan	58.19	55.63	7.71	4.83	4.61	0.64
26	3525	Gresik	47.50	37.12	12.05	3.55	2.74	0.88
27	3526	Bangkalan	52.53	38.39	29.38	5.25	3.81	2.89
28	3527	Sampang	40.05	17.95	10.13	4.01	1.78	0.99
29	3528	Pamekasan	21.38	17.82	1.64	2.39	1.97	0.18
30	3529	Sumenep	95.87	70.42	59.94	8.75	6.41	5.44
31	3571	Kediri City	3.01	5.51	1.16	1.03	1.88	0.40
32	3572	Blitar City	2.10	1.26	0.00	1.46	0.87	0.00
33	3573	Malang City	17.34	12.14	0.00	1.97	1.37	0.00
34	3574	Probolinggo City	1.64	3.98	0.00	0.68	1.64	0.00
35	3575	Pasuruan City	2.45	2.85	2.23	1.21	1.39	1.08
36	3576	Mojokerto City	1.05	1.45	0.00	0.80	1.10	0.00
37	3577	Madiun City	0.82	0.53	0.38	0.46	0.30	0.21
38	3578	Surabaya City	35.02	23.53	23.06	1.20	0.80	0.79
39	3579	Batu City	0.71	2.05	0.00	0.34	0.96	0.00

Notes:

* : Estimates are calculated by Badan Pusat Statistik (BPS)

** : Estimates are calculated by Satgas Data P3KE

Paying attention to table 3 above, it can be seen that the estimated number of extreme poverty (thousand people) in Kediri County: 21.60 (2021), 47.60 (2022); 12.25 (2023), and when viewed from the estimated extreme poverty rate (%) of Kediri County: 1.36 (2021), 2.99 (2022), 0.77 (2023).

When compared to surrounding districts, such as Tulungagung County: 9.83 (2021), 0.00 (2022); 0.00 (2023), and when viewed from the estimated extreme poverty rate (%) of Tulungagung County: 0.94 (2021), 0.00 (2022), 0.00 (2023). Jombang County: 29.51 (2021), 11.88 (2022); 6.39 (2023), and when viewed from the estimated extreme poverty rate (%) of Jombang County: 2.32 (2021), 0.93 (2022), 0.50 (2023). Nganjuk County: 11.81 (2021), 14.40 (2022); 5.69 (2023), and when viewed from the estimated extreme poverty rate (%) of Nganjuk County: 1.11 (2021), 1.36 (2022), 0.53 (2023). Blitar County: 5.22 (2021), 9.30 (2022); 3.36 (2023), and when viewed from the estimated extreme poverty rate (%) of Blitar County: 0.45 (2021), 0.79 (2022), 0.29 (2023).

Based on the description above, in general, Kediri County is still in a relatively high position in the number of extreme poverty when compared to the surrounding districts.

The condition of extreme poverty is still relatively high, due to the unclear division of authority in the implementation of management, including the collection of SDGs data, because all management is in the East Java provincial government, so that the Kediri district government is less concerned and lacks synergy with the government in the implementation of the acceleration of the elimination of extreme poverty in Kediri Regency. There is a collaboration between the ministry of social affairs and the East Java provincial government with the Kediri Regency Government as Humaira (2024) opined; Sumarnni and Yuningsih (2020); and Tanjung (2020) However, in accordance with the opinion of Li (2022), He & Tang (2021) that it is still not integrated in the implementation of the acceleration of extreme poverty eradication. In addition, the importance of synergy in terms

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of communication, coordination and cooperation between parties involved in the implementation of the president's instructions for the elimination of extreme poverty as agreed by Anggalaksana (2022) and Poespithadi (2023), Angga & Pradana (2021).

The need for the application of complementary principles that have an impact so that participation is needed, such as the construction of a machine consisting of several components according to the opinions of Feizabadi & Alibakhshi (2022) and Zhu et al., (2021) The involvement of all ministries and local governments can also provide subsidies so that there is synergy between parties, as suggested by Patil (2021). This condition does not appear in the implementation of the program, even though the local government, in particular, needs a lot of grants for the poor. The implementation of policies to accelerate the elimination of extreme poverty requires the cooperation of all government agencies. However, in reality in the field, there is still a lack of strong cooperation as suggested by Putri (2024), Supriyanto & Jannah (2022), Taruno (2022), Septiana & Tohopi (2024). Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to the suggestion that the formulated strategy can realize the strengthening of cross-sectoral regulations, risk reduction, realize the strengthening of an adaptive and responsive risk reduction management system and realize the development of a cooperative system. The process of health development is inseparable from cooperation between various sectors. Good coordination is needed to support optimal development results. Clarity is needed in the strict division of roles and responsibilities between the sectors involved so that development can be carried out optimally.

Pearce (2020) suggest the five key benefits to collaboration and show that with trust, understanding, and mutual respect, powerful and sustainable partnerships develop. On the contrary, Andrianus and Alfatih (2023) stated that the condition of sanitation, electricity, and road infrastructure has a significant negative effect on the poverty rate, in the sense that the improvement in each infrastructure has an impact on decreasing the percentage of poor people in Indonesia. Thus, it is proven that the increase in each element of sanitation, electricity and roads has a significant effect on the decrease in the percentage of the number of poor people in Indonesia. The conditions as described above, have not been fully experienced in Kediri district.

The results of Sopian's (2020) research can be used as a reference for the Kediri Regency Government, namely the number of Indonesia's poor population from year to year has decreased by an average of around 946,330 from 2015 to 2018. The results of the study show that 1) HDI does not have a positive effect (opposite) which means that when HDI rises poverty will decrease, 2) the level of education does not have a positive effect (opposite) which means that when the level of education rises poverty will decrease, 3) the unemployment rate has a positive effect which means that

when the unemployment rate decreases, the poverty rate also decreases 4) HDI, The level of education, the unemployment rate turns out to have a simultaneous effect on poverty in Indonesia. The conclusion in this study is that it turns out that HDI, education level, and unemployment rate have a partial or simultaneous effect.

The results of Salong (2024) research can also be used as a reference that average length of schooling (RLS), life expectancy (AHH), per capita income and poverty rate had a negative and significant effect on reducing the poverty rate. Paying attention to the description above, where in general the implementation of the INPRES policy Number 4 of 2022 concerning the Acceleration of the Elimination of Extreme Poverty, both at the national level, East Java province and Kediri Regency has not been optimal in holding the principles according to the INPRES policy, namely: integration, synergy and cooperation. The implication is that the implementation of the INPRES policy is less effective, so that the extreme poverty rate is still relatively high, when compared to the surrounding districts. This is in accordance with the opinion of Ferianto (2022) and Pratama (2023) who stated that basically effectiveness is used to show the success of a business or activity in order to achieve the set goals and if it is still not effective in some services occurs because there are several obstacles in the quantity of human resources, community demand factors that have not been fully met, handling in terms of administration, communication as well as knowledge and awareness of the community. Thus, the ineffectiveness of the implementation of the INPRES is because the Kediri Regency Government faces dominant obstacles such as: the communication system is not smooth, the lack of integration in planning and budgeting, the lack of synergy due to the separation of authority and the size of massive cooperation, between institutions involved in accelerating the elimination of extreme poverty.

CONCLUSION

The Central Government has issued Presidential Instruction Number 4 of 2022 concerning the Acceleration of the Elimination of Extreme Poverty. The implementation of Presidential Instruction Number 4 of 2022 requires integration, synergy and cooperation between ministries and local governments, so that the effectiveness of the implementation of policies to accelerate poverty eradication is less effective due to communication system constraints in cooperation between ministries and local governments, especially in human resource management and funding.

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